

“List of Company Challenges and Selected Co-Creation Teams”

DELIVERABLE	Version 04
D3.3	09 2025

Project Number: 101070297

Project Acronym: INDUSAC

Project title: Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations

Starting date: 01/09/2022

Duration in months: 36

Call (part) identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-20

Technical reference

<i>Deliverable:</i> 3.3	<i>List of Company Challenges and Selected Co-Creation Teams</i>
<i>Work Package:</i>	3
<i>Due Date:</i>	M35
<i>Submission Date:</i>	23/07/2025, resubmission: 19/09/2025
<i>Start Date of Project:</i>	01/09/2022
<i>Duration of Project:</i>	36 months
<i>Organisation Responsible for Deliverable:</i>	Jožef Stefan Institute
<i>Version:</i>	4.0
<i>Status:</i>	Final
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<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	INDUSAC partners and the INDUSAC Steering Committee
<i>Type:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Other
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> SEN

History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
16.05.2024	<i>initial draft by partners responsible</i>	V0.1
20.05.2024	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V0.2
27.05.2024	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V0.3
28.05.2024	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V1.0
05.11.2024	<i>draft M27 by partners responsible</i>	V1.1
08.11.2024	<i>draft M27 based on feedback by partners</i>	V1.2
20.11.2024	<i>draft M27 based on feedback by Steering Committee</i>	V1.3
29.11.2024	<i>final version M27 submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V2.0
23.05.2025	<i>draft M35 by partners responsible</i>	V2.1
28.05.2025	<i>draft M35 based on feedback by partners</i>	V2.2
06.06.2025	<i>draft M35 based on feedback by Steering Committee</i>	V2.3
23.07.2025	<i>final version M35 submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V3.0
19.09.2025	<i>final version M35 based on comments from final review meeting</i>	V4.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. The INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This deliverable contains the list of companies' Challenges published, and the list of co-creation teams assembled and having proceeded with their co-creation projects. This is an update of the previous versions of this deliverable (Odić et. al., 2024 a, b) and corresponds to all nine rounds of the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers (i. e. with cut-off dates 11.02.2024, 18.06.2024, 30.09.2024, 30.10.2024, 30.11.2024, 30.01.2025, 28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025). The deliverable assists in demonstrating the success rate of the INDUSAC mechanism. During the project, 251 Challenges were published and 164 teams received approval of their Motivation Letters by companies and started the co-creation projects.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
EU	European Union
F	Female
IAC	Industry-Academia Collaboration
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUStry- Academia Collaborations
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
M	Month (when followed by number) / Male (when referring to gender)
V	Version
W	Would rather not say

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I. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable contains the list of published Challenges submitted by companies, and of co-creation teams assembled and approved by companies, corresponding to the nine rounds of the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers. Note that “approved” or “selected” in the context of this deliverable refers to teams with approved Motivation Letters that had proceeded with their co-creation projects. Co-creation teams are grouped by individual rounds of the Call for Students and Researchers.

During the INDUSAC project:

- 164 Motivation Letters were approved by companies which equals 164 selected co-creation teams and 164 signed FSTP Declarations
- 163 co-creation teams submitted Solutions (1 team did not submit a Solution, see deliverable D3.5 (Kunej 2025))
- 159 Solutions were approved which equals 159 teams that received FSTP funds (4 teams submitted Solutions which were rejected, see deliverable D3.5 (Kunej 2025))

In this deliverable (D3.3) we refer to the 164 teams since the title is “List of Company Challenges and **Selected Co-Creation Teams**”.

In deliverable D3.5 (Monitoring and Evaluation Report (Kunej 2025)) we refer to the entire co-creation process, starting with 164 teams with approved Motivation Letters, out of which 163 lead to submitted Solutions. Out of those, 159 were approved and received FSTP funds.

In deliverable D3.6 (FSTP Agreements with Students and Researchers (Odić et al. 2025)) we list only the 159 FSTP declarations that refer to co-creation teams that submitted Solutions which were approved and **received FSTP funding**.

II. LIST OF COMPANY CHALLENGES

List of companies' Challenges published during the INDUSAC project is given below (in the format of [company name / Challenge title]). All Challenges are published on the INDUSAC platform.

The 100 Challenges published by February 2024:

1. **Scepter:** Herbie.IoT
2. **Kreal inženiring:** Eco Smart Board
3. **Envit:** ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening the Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide
4. **Ubiquity Robotics:** The Next Wave of Growth for Robots in Warehouse
5. **Ubiquity Robotics:** Robots for E-mobility - Can We Shape Nascent Government Policy?
6. **Virmedex:** The Global Perfusion Gaming Tournament
7. **Alpod:** Innovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors
8. **Orodjarstvo Križaj:** Innovative Diversification: Broadening Horizons in Die Casting Toolmaking
9. **Enrich 360:** AI Avatar Interactive Learning System for Cutting-Edge EdTech Platform
10. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute:** New Ideas to Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches
11. **Eurol:** Abrasive Innovation: Crafting a Marketing Campaign of the Future for Metalworking Industry
12. **Eurol:** Creating New Business Service for Metalworking Industry
13. **Libela orodja:** Smart Tools
14. **KyKLOIKOdromio:** Make Circular Economy Actions for All Profitable
15. **Smart Octopus Solutions:** Marketing and Selling Campaigns Based on Market Research
16. **Belinka Perkemija d.o.o.:** Project 3in1: Innovative Approaches to Discovering Consumer Needs: an In-Depth Detergent Market Overview and Trend Analysis
17. **Belinka Perkemija d.o.o.:** Project 3in1: Marketing Strategy for a Breakthrough Launch of an Innovative Product
18. **Wine That's Fruit Ltd.:** Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing
19. **Interstellar Space Technologies LTD:** In-Space Microgravity Manufacturing of High Temperature Super Alloys
20. **Interstellar Space Technologies LTD:** Cosmic Campaigns: Marketing the Future of Space Manufacturing
21. **Martin Pečar (OmniOpti):** Network and weather influence model
22. **Robocon:** Business Plan for Digitalization and Automation Solution for the Construction Site and Prefab Atelier
23. **GeoCodis Ltd.:** Marketing Campaign for Satellite-based Application MyPhotoFromSpace

24. **Hella Saturnus Slovenia:** Market Analysis and Trendspotting of Automotive Lighting Products with Focus on End Customer
25. **Trixin:** Office of the Future: Tech to Wellbeing
26. **Phasmatic Private Company:** Marketing Campaign for 3D Presentation In Online Shops
27. **Fluidra:** Water and Energy Saving in Aquatics Centres Facilities
28. **Gábor Hertbert PBGSZ:** Re-Thought of an Energy-Efficient Office Building in a County Capital of Hungary
29. **Gábor Hertbert PBGSZ:** Market and Trend Analysis for an Energy Efficient Office Building in a Hungarian County Capital
30. **Gábor Hertbert PBGSZ:** Marketing Campaign for an Energy Efficient Office Building in a Hungarian County Capital
31. **Gábor Hertbert PBGSZ:** SWOT Analysis of an Energy Efficient Office Building in Operation in a County Capital of Hungary
32. **The Southwest Hungarian Engineering Cluster:** Increasing Social Media Popularity in the Non-Profit Sector
33. **Khoani Bördíszműgyártó és Kereskedelmi Kft.:** RFID Passive Protection
34. **FerroČrtalič:** Advancements In Orthopedic and Dental Implant Surface Treatments
35. **Klančar žerjavi:** Breaking into the Italian Market: a Construction Crane Company's Journey
36. **Jub Group:** What kind of Products / Services Young People will be Looking for in the Future in the Segment of Wall Paints?
37. **Kolpa:** Aluminum Oxide Powder with Active Surface to be Used as Catalyst in Other Chemical Processes
38. **Novitech:** Electricity Cost Saving of Manufacturing SMEs
39. **Plastika Skaza:** Marketing Campaign of the Future: Composting Solutions
40. **Plastika Skaza:** Strategic Development of Product Roadmap
41. **Animacel:** Competitive Landscape Analysis of Microcarriers and ATMPs
42. **Animacel:** Analysis of Competitive Landscape of Current Surgical Management of Gastrointestinal Tract Perforations
43. **Quipnex:** Elevating Qx Application Sales: Crafting an Irresistible Consulting Approach for Researchers
44. **Quipnex:** Strategic Expansion into International Markets: Crafting a Future-Focused Marketing Plan
45. **SciFitLab:** Informing Clients about Provided Services and Client Outreach
46. **Cytanet:** Transitioning From a Physical-Type Company to a Digital One
47. **Hidria:** Battery Electric Vehicles - Product Opportunities
48. **Ubiquity Robotics:** Robot Fleet Manager from Open-Source Software
49. **Beti:** Marketing Campaign for Metalized / Conductive Yarns
50. **Gazek:** Developing a Digital Platform in the Field of Fall Safety – Create Gazek App
51. **Gazek:** Branding in the Hungarian Market – Gazek - The Fall Safety Expert
52. **Gazek:** Recycling Gazek Safety Products – Responsibility for All, for Everything

53. **Enviral Oberflächenveredelung GmbH:** How to Promote a Digital Price Calculator in the Coating Industry?
54. **Chrysalis LEAP:** Online Media Monitoring Tool
55. **Promocija in poslovne storitve Nataša Skubic s.p.:** Developing Virtual Bar Caffe of the Future
56. **Promocija in poslovne storitve Nataša Skubic s.p.:** Development of Additional Services in a Traditional Bar Caffe
57. **Ham:** Dynamic Sitting Marketing Campaign (SpinaliS)
58. **Ham:** Marketing Campaign for Green Mobile Solution RolUet
59. **Uazo Tech Ltd.:** How to Survive As a Small Company in the IT-Sector
60. **Biokoda:** How to Promote a Solution on Need-to-Know Basis
61. **Acoustic Technologies:** How to Turn a User's Business Model into a Rental or Sale Business Model
62. **Project Brains:** Market Reseach for a Project Brains (A future of Work Platform)
63. **Hidrofilt Ltd.:** Chlorine Gas Produced from FeCl_3 by Membrane Electrolysis
64. **Project Brains:** From Gen AI to Business Development at Scale.
65. **Hidrofilt Ltd.:** Simultaneous Production of Chlorine Gas and Sodium Ferrate
66. **iFinance Consulting Kft.:** Innovative Financial Controlling Service Development, Unleashing Cutting-Edge Controlling Solutions for SMEs
67. **Hidrofilt Ltd.:** Removal of Micropollutants from Municipal Wastewater
68. **H-CAM S.A.:** New Marketing Campaign of Hellenic CAM S.A.
69. **Brygge GmbH:** Find the Key Persona for Brygge and Design a Successful Marketing Campaign Incl. Landing Page for Them
70. **Ham:** pla:Fi the Innovative Pillow, Marketing Campaign
71. **Alpha Ponte Sp. z.o.o.:** Develop a Future Production Line
72. **Quipnex:** LIMS Evolution: Advancing Open Science and Integrating AI Solutions
73. **RHP Technology GmbH:** Precious Nanoparticles and their Applications
74. **Brygge GmbH:** Age-friendly Banking and Fraud Prevention
75. **ABIX (Austrian Bit Experts) GmbH:** How to Promote a Simulator for the Microprocessor Industry?
76. **Jafral:** Healthy Microbial Ecosystem of the Gastrointestinal Tract (GIT)
77. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute:** Future Approaches in Organic Skincare Marketing Initiatives
78. **Jafral:** Vector Systems (Gene Delivery Vehicles) Used in Manufacturing of Gene Therapy Medicinal Products (GTMPs)
79. **H-CAM S.A.:** Services of Hellenic CAM S.A.
80. **Brygge GmbH:** Fun and Easy-to-Use "Financial Competence Training & Knowledge Service" for People 50+
81. **Strip's:** Market and Trend Analysis of Healthy Drinks Market, Entry to the Market with Immunity Lemonade
82. **Strip's:** Market and Trend Analysis of Consumer Trends among Beekeepers' Population

83. **Wojciech Poćwiardowski (Fizjo-Estetica):** New Methods of Non-Invasive Face and Body Lifts
84. **Earth Kidney Sp. z o.o.:** Development of a Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System
85. **Gen Studio:** Mental Well-Being of People With Dementia - Market Analysis of Extra-Curricular Education in Nursing Homes / Home-Care Agencies in Field of Dementia
86. **Sparsity, S.L.:** Digitalization of the Knowledge of the University as a Provider of Talent
87. **Galoha Company SL:** Growing the Appeal of Galoha
88. **H-CAM S.A.:** New Services & Product Ideas for Hellenic CAM S.A.
89. **Exolum:** Study of the State of the Art of Green Hydrogen Storage in Solid Supports for the Development of a Technological Solution.
90. **Acoustic Technologies:** Virtual Prototype of 3D Modeled and Printed Acoustic Shelves
91. **Shrink Wrap Ltd:** Innovating in the Mental Health Sector
92. **Shrink Wrap Ltd:** Estimating the Profitability of an Innovation in the Mental Health Sector
93. **Shrink Wrap Ltd:** Road to Market for New Innovation in Mental Health Sector
94. **Iskra mehanizmi (Intelligent Mechanotronics):** Market & Trend Analysis of Future Use of Actuators In Automotive and Industrial Market Segments
95. **Solar Key Development Ltd:** Business Plan for Establishing a Construction Division in a Renewable Energy Company
96. **Eurol:** Sustainability Challenge: Reducing Waste in Abrasive Materials Production
97. **MUnique Technology:** Marketing Strategy for time & Frequency Synchronisation System
98. **Etiketa d.d.:** Product Labelling of the Future
99. **Martin Pečar (OmniOpti):** Automatic SEO System
100. **Columbia Ship Management:** Maritime IT Fusion: Integrating GPT-Like Large Language Models for Enhanced PDF Processing in the Maritime Industry

The 29 Challenges published between February and September 2024:

101. **Healthy Cities:** Business Plan for a Digital Tool on Healthy Urban Planning
102. **Cytanet:** Marketing Campaign
103. **DigitalLeather d.o.o.:** Selection of the Equipment to Support System for Digitization of Entire, Natural, Industrially Processed Animal Leather in order to Detect Defects.
104. **Connect IQ Sp. z.o.o.:** Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ
105. **ENVIT, environmental engineering and technologies Ltd.:** Redesign and Updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website to Enhance Global Engagement and Accessibility

106. **EIT Climate-KIC:** Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)
107. **Malsch TechnoValuation:** Adapting Ethical Impact Assessment Methodology to Needs of Innovative Companies
108. **Malsch TechnoValuation:** Young People Live Sustainably
109. **Orodjarstvo Križaj:** AEPAP: from Advanced Engineering Prototypes to Actual Production
110. **Gumiks:** Protective Working Equipment
111. **Incom Leone:** Unlocking Market Potential: Comprehensive Analysis of Healthy Ice Creams for the Health-Conscious Consumer
112. **Personel System:** Sales Strategy for an Accredited Coaching Course
113. **Urb4nowicz, Ewa Grudowska:** Beyond Traditional Envelopes: Redefining Communication with SmartEnvelope
114. **Naisignifica.com:** Reaching New SME Clients
115. **Naisignifica.com:** Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies
116. **Lifocolor.pl:** Developing a Smart Color Identification Online / Mobile App
117. **ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA S.A.:** Storage-as-a-Service. Imagining and defining new services to raise consumers into flexumers
118. **ENVIT, Environmental Engineering and Technologies Ltd. :** Optimizing ENVIT's ReSoil® Website for Enhanced Performance, Branding, and User Experience
119. **Connect IQ Sp. z.o.o.:** ESG & Carbon Footprint Calculation Platform: Automating CO₂ Tracking and Reporting
120. **Connect IQ Sp. z.o.o.:** Shaping the Future of Machine Efficiency: Understanding Customer Needs for OEE Optimization
121. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.:** New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare
122. **IMG Építő Ltd.:** Design of Thermal Break for Exterior Windows and Doors
123. **Zakład Sprzętu Ortopedycznego i Rehabilitacyjnego Spółka z Ograniczoną Odpowiedzialnością:** Development of a Promotional Campaign Promoting Students who Graduated from School Obtained Qualifications in Training as a Shoemaker, i.e. a Person who Sews Orthopedic Shoes
124. **Trilobit:** Tennis Academy Assistant
125. **EPS Teknoloji Elektronik Makine Tekstil San. ve Tic. Ltd. :** Export and Overseas Market Challenges
126. **Slovenski gledališki inštitut:** Tools for Presenting and Searching Through our Collections
127. **Alveus:** Alveus Kitchen Sink: The Centerpiece of Your Kitchen
128. **Alveus:** Alveus Kitchen Sinks: Digital Platform Design & Enhancement
129. **Hidria:** AI Assistants: Automating and Streamlining Engineering Processes

The 122 Challenges published from September 2024 through March 2025:

130. **Agitavit Solutions d.o.o.:** Channel Analysis for eHRM Market Entry in Serbia
131. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.:** Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion
132. **Agitavit Solutions d.o.o.:** Marketing Strategy for Low-Code Platform Solution
133. **Agitavit Solutions d.o.o.:** Innovative B2B Solutions Through Cross-Industry Collaboration Challenge
134. **Agitavit Solutions d.o.o.:** Developing a Sales Partnership Network for eHRM in Serbia
135. **Anderson Group Kft.:** Marketing Strategy for Finding American Partners for Anderson Group Hungary Kft. in the SSC Industry
136. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.:** Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare
137. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.:** Development and Execution of a Social Media Strategy for Tower Spa
138. **Anderson Group Kft.:** Enhancing Efficiency by at Least 20% in Anderson Group's SSC with ChatGPT in the Call Center Domain
139. **Ivánics György:** New Sustainable Service Offerings in a Family-Owned Restaurant
140. **Ivánics György:** Developing Sustainable Event Services and Methodology for Restaurants
141. **Airbridge Global:** Autonomous Infrastructure Product Progression
142. **Airbridge Global:** Airbridge Go To Market
143. **Ivánics György:** Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector
144. **Meltica:** Solving Problems in the 3D Printing Industry Using Social Networks and AI Tools.
145. **Meltica:** Knowledge Base Related to Problems and their Solution from the Tool and Processing Industry for Injection Molding Technology
146. **Promocija in poslovne storitve, Nataša Skubic s.p.:** Virtual Bar Caffee: Functional Development, Optimization and SEO Strategy
147. **Nexus Energía S.A.:** Energy-Related Regulation Scenarios in Europe in 2030
148. **Hermi d.o.o.:** Implementation of AI Systems in the Metal Processing Industry (Small and Medium Sized Production)
149. **DACSM House Control Ltd:** Marketing Campaign Development for a Small Family Business
150. **DACSM House Control Ltd:** Designing an Engaging and Functional Website for a Small Business
151. **DACSM House Control Ltd:** Business Expansion Planning
152. **Taras Shnyder:** Development of a Method of Gluing Reinforced Concrete Structures with the Formation of a Waterproof Joint

153. **Zalóżba Rokus Klett d.o.o.:** Crack the Code: Help us Connect with the Next Gen of Learners Online
154. **Limara:** Renovation Cost Estimator App
155. **Siropol:** Integration of Data from Injection Molding Machines and Peripheral Devices.
156. **Lifocolor:** A tool for the Salesperson to Search for Potential Customers
157. **AMS International Sp. z.o.o.:** How to Effectively Promote TEBIS CAD / CAM Software within the INDUSAC Project as a Key Tool to Support Innovation and Digital Transformation in Industry.
158. **NanoPolí centar d.o.o.:** BossFacade-EcoFacade
159. **PLASTECH Pawel Wisniewski S.K.A.:** Redesign of B2B Offers Section on Plastech.pl
160. **And-Less:** Circular Business Model for Sustainable Reusable Packaging in the Food Service Industry
161. **SPE Labs sp. z.o.o.:** Marketing Campaign for Metal-Forming Defects Sensors
162. **Holkap:** Optimization of Logistics Costs in the Era of Factories 4.0
163. **Kancelaria Radców Prawnych Bartosz Sadowski:** Compatibility of ICT Programs for Law Firms and ICT Systems of the Justice System.
164. **Halmod Group Spółka z Organiczną Odpowiedzialnością Jakub Kocjan:** Innovating Modular Construction: Strategic Market Entry into Eastern and Northern Europe
165. **Fanuc Europe:** Innovative Product or Gadget Concepts for Electric Injection Molding Machines, Leveraging Industrial Automation and with Potential as a Promotional Item
166. **GRYDSEN sp.z.o.o.:** Business Models for the Implementation and Provision of Services for the Elderly Using the Innovative GRYDSEN Therapeutic Kit, Using Virtual Reality
167. **Psychological Solutions Group Agencja Analiz i Doradztwa Personalnego Remigiusz Koc:** Marketing Campaign of the Future
168. **Psychological Solutions Group Agencja Analiz i Doradztwa Personalnego Remigiusz Koc:** Lead Generation Tool
169. **Project Ahead:** Enhancing Visibility and Attractiveness of Our Co-working Space for International and Local Communities
170. **TVG Institute Milan Zrim:** Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications
171. **Polfin d.o.o.:** Forecasting and Predicting Customer's Behaviour and their Ability for Repaying their Obligations
172. **KAPlast:** Project 1: Product Utilizing Post-Production Re grind
173. **KAPlast:** Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging
174. **KAPlast:** Project 3: Innovative and Useful Product
175. **Trace Tech Id Solutions SL:** Optimization of the Marketing Strategy for the French Market.

176. **Forum Colorum d.o.o.:** Forum Universe as a Market Place for Car Refinish Portfolio B2B and B2C
177. **Siropol:** Electronic Document Circulation with Confirmation of Receipt
178. **IKEA Slovenija:** Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia
179. **Politech Sp. z o.o.:** Online 3D Creator of Cosmetic Products and Packaging Politech. Personalization of the Design and Vision of the Final Packaging
180. **Siropol:** Optimization of Energy Consumption in Production.
181. **IKEA Slovenija:** Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers
182. **Trace Tech Id Solutions SL:** Uncovering the Reason Behind the Failures of UHF-RFID when Exposed to Microwave Environments, Even When Protected.
183. **Alpha Ponte Sp. z o.o.:** Recycling 3D Printing Waste
184. **Alpha Ponte Sp. z o.o.:** Bioprinting - Future Technology for Tissues and Drugs
185. **Alpha Ponte Sp. z o.o.:** Post-Production Process Automation: Designing a System for the Automatic Removal of Supports and Surface Smoothing of 3D Prints.
186. **DCR S.A.:** Method for Cleaning 210 and 216.5 L Steel Barrels from Adhesive Residue.
187. **Greenagro:** Internationalisation of Greenagro Products and Services
188. **Greenagro:** Educational Center at Greenagro
189. **BEYOND MOTORS D.O.O.:** Contactless Temperature Sensor
190. **GALMED:** Portable Chair for Disabled and Elderly People
191. **Fortissimo srls:** Digital Music Education Innovation
192. **GALMED:** Medical Devices Advertisement According to MDR
193. **Lifocolor:** Educational LinkedIn Campaign: Recycling Facts, Myths, and Proper Waste Sorting Practices
194. **Airbridge Global:** Autonomous Infrastructure Simulator
195. **Airbridge Global:** Autonomous Roof Structure for Drone Hub
196. **2rays Solar:** Decarbonisation and Energy Efficiency Made Simple
197. **Airbridge Global:** Chain of Custody for Autonomous Delivery Solution
198. **Adriana Perez Legal Services:** Enhancing Digital Marketing of a Small International Fiscal & Law Firm
199. **ASYA GRAFY BIO INSTITUTE d.o.o.:** Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations
200. **Urb4nowicz, Ewa Grudowska:** New Approach for Designing a Campaign Based on Market Analysis Taking into Account Customer Needs and Trend Analysis
201. **Miss Polyplexi:** Marketing Campaign of the Future
202. **Coeco d.o.o.:** Illuminating the Invisible: UV-visible Marking on Recycled Paper
203. **Tlakovci Podlesnik d.o.o.:** Croatian Market Research Regarding the Sale of Concrete Products

204. **Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.:** Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation
205. **ENVIT, Environmental Engineering and Technologies Ltd.:** Engineering and Design of a Portable ReSoil® Demonstration Trailer for On-Site Soil Remediation
206. **ENVIT, Environmental Engineering and Technologies Ltd.:** ReSoil® Website Digital Optimization, SEO Strategy, and User Engagement
207. **4D Consulting Kft.:** AI-Powered EU Grant Advisory Platform Development for Scientific Innovations
208. **4D Consulting Kft.:** Personalized Innovation Funding Alert System: Intelligent Newsletter Platform for Research Competitions
209. **4D Consulting Kft.:** Innovation Ecosystem Matchmaking Platform: Expert-Innovator Connection Hub for Technology Commercialization
210. **Rovigo Sp. z o.o.:** Digitization of production
211. **HALMOD GROUP SPÓŁKA Z OGRANICZONĄ ODPOWIEDZIALNOŚCIĄ:** Innovating modular construction: strategic market entry into Northern America
212. **EDM TOOLS GROUP SP. Z O.O.:** Cutting optimization
213. **Holkap sp. z o.o.:** IoT platform
214. **PW BRAT:** Wheel protector
215. **Holkap sp. z o.o.:** An energy-efficient office building
216. **Politech Sp. z o.o.:** Creating a B2B Marketing Campaign for High-Quality decoration cosmetic packaging and plastic components various industries
217. **Politech Sp. z o.o.:** AI-Powered Packaging Design – Future Service and Product Innovation
218. **VPL d.o.o.:** Identifying Market Gaps and Innovation through Plastic Metallization for Business Growth
219. **VPL d.o.o.:** Creating a B2B Marketing Campaign for High-Quality Coating and Metallization Services in Industry
220. **VPL d.o.o.:** Development of a Digital Platform based on a Market Analysis in Coating and Metallization Industry
221. **EDM TOOLS GROUP SP. Z O.O.:** Graphite dust - waste today, semi-finished product tomorrow
222. **Vicim Poland Sp. z o.o.:** Review of New Restrictions on Product Packaging and Labeling and Analysis of Impact on the Market
223. **Vicim Poland Sp. z o.o.:** Analysis of Automotive Market Expectations Regarding the Use of 2K Technology: Review of Solutions, Investment Profitability, Market Capability to Ensure Minimum Production, and Identification of Potential Market Needs
224. **Vicim Poland Sp. z o.o.:** Project Inquiry: Finding Substitute Fillers During the Production of Thermoplastic Elastomers (TPE)
225. **Instrumentation Technologies:** RF Signal Generator Instruments for Quantum Laser Experiments

226. **SPE Labs sp. z o.o.:** Configuration of Grafana platform for visualizing the data from sensors.
227. **Mikroelektronika a.d. Banja Luka:** Microelectronic Industry PCB boards recycling (PCB-REC)
228. **NanoPoli Centre:** Cellulose Reinvented
229. **CAPITAL A.M. ltd Skopje:** Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"
230. **ASYA GRAFY BIO INSITUTE d.o.o.:** Innovative Skincare Formulation: Advanced Research and Optimization
231. **ASYA GRAFY BIO INSITUTE d.o.o.:** Eco-Friendly Solvents for Cosmetics: Harnessing the Power of DES
232. **ASYA GRAFY BIO INSITUTE d.o.o.:** Elevating Tower Spa's Brand Through Engaging Digital Content
233. **Energa TM d.o.o.:** AI-Optimized Energy Sharing Community with Smart Energy Trading and Automated Billing
234. **SPIN-PACK Innovations:** Developing & Testing a Low-Cost Sustainable Insulation or Monitoring Solution for Temperature-Sensitive Logistics
235. **ML Polyolefins SP. Z O.O.:** Strategy for Increasing ML Polyolefins' Brand Recognition in European Markets
236. **ML Polyolefins SP. Z O.O.:** Analysis of Plastic Product Distributors for DIY and Construction Retail Chains and Identification of Key Decision-Makers
237. **Hotic d.o.o.:** AI driven heavy construction machinery
238. **ML Polyolefins SP. Z O.O.:** Analysis of Gaps in Competitors' PR Activities and Development of a Differentiation Strategy for Stella Green
239. **EMO FRITE D.O.O.:** Market Analysis and Application of Glass Frits in the Foundry and Metallurgical Industry
240. **ML Polyolefins SP. Z O.O.:** Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation
241. **ML Polyolefins SP. Z O.O.:** Automated Real-Time Competitor Price Analysis Tool for Stella Green
242. **ML Polyolefins SP. Z O.O.:** Building Two Complementary Databases of B2B Clients and Construction Project Stakeholders for Stella Green
243. **EMO FRITE D.O.O.:** Market Analysis for Micronutrient Fertilizers in a Silicate Glass Matrix
244. **EMO FRITE D.O.O.:** AI-Integrated Production Planning for Batch-Based Manufacturing
245. **Hoply d.o.o.:** Hoply: Safe, and affordable rides for kids, simplifying after-school transportation for families
246. **PIW Delta Sp. z o.o.:** Development of an intumescent fire-retardant varnish for protecting outdoor wooden surfaces.

- 247. **HORPOL A. Horeczy Sp. K.:** Innovative lighting product for automotive industry that solve the customer pain
- 248. **CAPITAL A.M. ltd Skopje:** Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services
- 249. **HORPOL A. Horeczy Sp. K.:** Innovative Marketing and Sales Campaigns of the Future for HORPOL A. Horeczy Sp. K.
- 250. **Earth Kidney Sp. z o.o.:** Development of a New, Innovative Filter Bed for the Filtration of Swimming Pool Water
- 251. **BOOST Tourism:** Research Tourist future expectations in-destination

III. LIST OF SELECTED CO-CREATION TEAMS

A list of co-creation teams comprising students and researchers that have started working on individual co-creation projects, corresponding to the nine rounds of the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers (i. e., with cut-off dates 11.02.2024, 18.06.2024, 30.09.2024, 30.10.2024, 30.11.2024, 30.01.2025, 28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025), is given below. For each team in the list, the title of the Challenge is followed by the team's ID number, name and surname, gender (F – female, M – male, W-would rather not say), country of residency / country of university (the latter for students only), and status (student or researcher) of individual team members.

The 15 teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved 15 Motivation Letters and 15 signed FSTP Declarations) in the 1st round (cut-off date 11.02.2024) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Aluminum oxide powder with active surface to be used as catalyst in other chemical processes

273053	Anja Svajger (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Lenart Žežlina (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Margareth Pariguana (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Nina Kovač (F)	Slovenia / -	researcher
	Sabi W Konsago (M)	Slovenia / -	researcher
	Yasin Sahin (M)	Turkey / Turkey	student

ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide

443055	Md Abdul Roshid (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Mohammad Zeeshan (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Elene Miminoshvili (F)	Georgia / Georgia	student
	Vineeta Taneja (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Geeta Reemoh (M)	Germany / Germany	student

Transitioning From A Physical-Type Company To A Digital One

414063	Manal Abbes (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Parnian Kashani (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Makhosi Khuzawyo (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Ekombong Okopido (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Ahlam Boubekri (F)	Morocco / Hungary	student
	Noureddine Hfaiedh (M)	Tunisia / Hungary	student

Battery electric vehicles - product opportunities

330066	Nina Kovač (F)	Slovenia / -	researcher
	Md Mehedi Hasan (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	student
	Anja Svajger (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Sabi William Konsago (M)	Slovenia / -	researcher
	Tim Hrovat (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Tanuj Namboodri (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student

Robot fleet manager from open-source software

447068	kawtar dhaidah (F)	Morocco / Hungary	student
	Muhammad Hamza Daud (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Moenes Benaissa (M)	Tunisia / Hungary	student
	Ahmad Asaad (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Ibrahim Shaglil (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student

RECYCLING GAZEK SAFETY PRODUCTS - RESPONSIBILITY FOR ALL FOR EVERYTHING

366074	Ana Teresa Sucgang (F)	France / France	student
	Brandon Joshua A. Gococo (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Inga Werecka (F)	Poland / Hungary	student
	Solmaz Hajjalilou (F)	Hungary / Germany	student

RECYCLING GAZEK SAFETY PRODUCTS - RESPONSIBILITY FOR ALL FOR EVERYTHING

356074	Ramin Mahmoudi (M)	Finland / Finland	student
	Eszter Borsodi (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Matevž Gortnar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student

Marketing campaign for green mobile solution RolUet

302081	ELENA ORFANIDOU (F)	Cyprus / Cyprus	student
	Hanif Ahmad (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	student
	Luka Rakovič (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Tanja Luznar (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student

Removal Of Micropollutants From Municipal Wastewater

247090	Egzona Osmani (F)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	student
	Nina Kovač (F)	Slovenia / -	researcher
	Ramin Mahmoudi (M)	Finland / Finland	student
	Selly Ayu Janetasari (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Victor Kweku Ayertey (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	student

pla:Fi the innovative pillow marketing campaign

402093	Elena Orfanidou (F)	Cyprus / Cyprus	student
	Matevž Gortnar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Tanuj Namboodri (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Tanja Luznar (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student

Age-friendly banking and fraud prevention

484098	Jakub Burek (M)	Poland / Poland	student
	Cotogoi Mihaela (F)	Moldova / Romania	student
	Hasa Ovidiu Alexandru (M)	Romania / Romania	student

Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives

1800101	Nina Furman (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Marko Jovanović (M)	Serbia / -	researcher
	Ana Kolinger (F)	Croatia / Croatia	student

Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives

4090101	Mihailo Milićević (M)	Serbia / Serbia	student
	Jana Delač (F)	Croatia / Croatia	student
	Aleksander Breznikar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student

Fun and easy to use "financial competence training & knowledge service" for people 50+

5000105	Nina Tušek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Matevž Gortnar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Antonija Karin (F)	Croatia / Croatia	student
	Bogdan Buzadzic (M)	Serbia / Slovenia	student

Innovative diversification: broadening horizons in die casting toolmaking

4000119	Ramin Mahmoudi (M)	Finland / Finland	student
	Idd Yunusu (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Tanuj Namboodri (M)	Hungary / Hungary	student
	Moenes Benaissa (M)	Tunisia / Hungary	student
	Wafae el Majdoub (F)	Hungary / Hungary	student

Correction note: In the M27 version of this deliverable (Odić et al. 2024b) the number of listed teams was 16. This number has been corrected in this version to 15 because the previously listed team with the company-approved Motivation Letter had decided not to proceed with the co-creation project.

The 13 teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved 13 Motivation Letters and 13 signed FSTP Declarations) in the 2nd round (cut-off date 18.06.2024) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors

6990103	Črt Švajger (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	student
	Kosta Jovanovic (M)	BiH / BiH	Student
	Mateja Srblijinović (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Tennis academy assistant

2830167	Ajša Džindo (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Antonija Karin (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Gašper Škof (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Lev KiarAvberšek (M)	Belgium / Belgium	Researcher

Redesign And Updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website To Enhance Global Engagement And Accessibility

7500174	Angelina Apostoloska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Borko Petrevski (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Stefana Spirkoska (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student

Product labelling of the future

8550143	Alexander Delobel (M)	Cyprus / Cyprus	Student
	Ana Arsovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Tajda Hladnik (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Sustainability Challenge: Reducing Waste In Abrasive Materials Production

4470140	Aimen Tanougast (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Muhammad Ahmad (M)	Finland / Finland	Student
	Muhammad Hamza Daud (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Wafae El Majdoub (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	IDD MOHAMED YUNUSU (M)	Hungary /Hungary	Student

Redesign And Updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website To Enhance Global Engagement And Accessibility

4430174	Md Abdul Roshid (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Elene Miminoshvili (F)	Georgia / Georgia	Student
	Geeta Reemoh (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Mohammad Zeeshan (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Zainab Fatima (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Precious Nanoparticles And Their Applications

312097	Lei Han (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Ana Gubenšek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Amina Selmanović (F)	BiH / Slovenia	Student
	Mariem Zouari (F)	Tunisia / Slovenia	Student
	Wojciech Pajerski (M)	Slovenia / -	Researcher
	Rene Alexander Diaz (M)	Slovenia / -	Researcher

New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches

4090132	Aleksander Breznikar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Jana Delač (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Jelena Grujicic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches

1800132	Gabriela Suša (W)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Nina Furman (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sara Epet (W)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Smart Tools

7770139	Abedin S. M. Ashik (M)	Turkey / Turkey	Student
	Ahmed Faisal (M)	Hungary / -	Researcher
	Mritika Roy (F)	Germany / Germany	Student
	IDD MOHAMED YUNUSU (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Advancements In Orthopedic And Dental Implant Surface Treatments

649049	Ecaterina Cârstea Alexia (F)	Romania / Romania	Student
	Dan Laptoiu (M)	Romania / -	Researcher
	Florin Miculescu (M)	Romania / -	Researcher
	Lucian Toma Ciocan (M)	Romania / -	Researcher
	Marco Truccato (M)	Italy / -	Researcher
	Silviu Colis (M)	France / -	Researcher

Developing virtual bar caffe of the future

778078	Eda Nur KAÇAKÇI (F)	Turkey / Turkey	Student
	Lali Kurdadze (F)	Georgia / Georgia	Student
	Fatima Zainab (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Marketing campaign for metalized/conductive yarns

482069	Ashik Abedin (M)	Turkey / Turkey	Student
	Ahmed Faisal (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Mritika Roy (F)	Germany / Germany	Student

Correction note: In the M27 version of this deliverable (Odić et al. 2024b) the number of listed teams was 15. This number has been corrected in this version to 13 because one previously listed team was moved to the first round of co-creation projects and another team was removed from the list because it had been accidentally duplicated in the records.

The twelve teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved twelve Motivation Letters and twelve signed FSTP Declarations) in the 3rd round (cut-off date 30.09.2024) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Marketing Campaign For An Energy Efficient Office Building In A Hungarian County Capital

656042	Gašper Gortnar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Haniye Shojaee (W)	Bulgaria / Bulgaria	Student
	Kosta Jovanovic (M)	BiH / BiH	Student

SWOT Analysis Of An Energy Efficient Office Building In Operation In A County Capital Of Hungary

958043	Haniye Shojaee (W)	Bulgaria / Bulgaria	Student
	Gašper Gortnar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Margareth Carla Pariguana (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Increasing Social Media Popularity In The Non-Profit Sector

955044	Haniye Shojaee (W)	Bulgaria / Bulgaria	Student
	Meta Švagelj (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Ujmir Uka (M)	Kosovo / N. Macedonia	Student

New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches

9340132	Ilyas El Bourari (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Jasna Smilkov (F)	Croatia / Slovenia	Student
	Matic Krašovic (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Project 3in1: Innovative Approaches to Discovering Consumer Needs. An In-Depth Detergent Market Overview and Trend Analysis

9670144	Dino Andreevski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Jana Jovanoska (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Jovana Asterija Nakova (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Marketing And Selling Campaigns Based On Market Research

9650145	Dino Andreevski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Jana Jovanoska (F)	N. Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Jovana Asterija Nakova (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ

9440173	Ilyas El Bourari (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Jasna Smilkov (F)	Croatia / Slovenia	Student
	Matic Krašovic (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Unlocking Market Potential: Comprehensive Analysis of Healthy Ice Creams for the Health-Conscious Consumer

9090183	Ilyas El Bourari (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Jasna Smilkov (F)	Croatia / Slovenia	Student
	Maksim Dovečar (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Matic Krašovic (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Beyond Traditional Envelopes: Redefining Communication with SmartEnvelope

9560187	Aleksandra Trifunoska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Elio Corradini (W)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Hristijan Markoski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Leonid Boshoski (M)	Slovenia / N. Macedonia	Student

Optimizing ENVIT's ReSoil® Website for Enhanced Performance, Branding, and User Experience

7500196	Angelina Apostoloska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Borko Petrevski (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Stefana Spirkoska (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student

New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

4090202	Aleksander Breznikar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Jana Delač (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Jelena Grujicic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

1800202	Gabriela Suša (W)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Nina Furman (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sara Epet (W)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

The seven teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved seven Motivation Letters and seven signed FSTP Declarations) in the 4th round (cut-off date 30.10.2024) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations

10420201	Lučka Kaligarič (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Martina Mileva (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marija Ristovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Vanja Angjelovikj (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marko Arsov (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student

Alveus kitchen sink: The centerpiece of your kitchen

4990191	Antonija Karin (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Marko Lui (M)	Belgium / Belgium	Student
	Andrea Anna Milin (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations

2230201	Karla Marinović (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Marko Jovanović (M)	Serbia / -	Researcher
	Sandra Mikić (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Olivera Delic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Tamara Attard (F)	Malta / -	Researcher

Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations

10550201	Damjan Georgievski (M)	Belgium / Belgium	Student
	Iva Edrovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Kostadin Mitkov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

AI Assistants: Automating and Streamlining Engineering Processes

2730197	Anja Svajger (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Martin Georgievski (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Stefanos H Panagiotou (M)	Greece / Greece	Student
	Tim Hrovat (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Timotej Šuman (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably

9510179	Mohamad Ali (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Pavel Aftimiciuc (M)	Moldova / Hungary	Student
	Piotr Mazur (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Nasibakhon Rasulova (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)

9620176	Egzona Osmani (F)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student
	Maša Kralj (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Md Mehedi Hasan (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student

The six teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved six Motivation Letters and six signed FSTP Declarations) in the 5th round (cut-off date 30.11.2024) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Office of the future: tech to wellbeing

10150164	Margarita Stafanowitch (F)	Cyprus / -	Researcher
	Mariia Panasiuk (F)	Ukraine / Ukraine	Student
	Masha Schneider (F)	Slovakia / -	Researcher
	Valentyna Panasiuk (W)	Poland / Ukraine	Student

New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

11450202	Dragan Jovanovski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sabrina Jurkošek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Maša Čorović (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Autonomous Roof Structure for Drone Hub

11520209	Ajhan Skenderoski (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	João PSM dos Santos (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student
	Slavica Dimkoska (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide

878055	João PSM dos Santos (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student
	Tamara Trajkovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Zdravko Brdarovski (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing

9240150	Hanif Ahmad (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Julija Miladinovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Lucijana Kraljević (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably

10150179	Margarita Stafanowitch (F)	Cyprus / -	Researcher
	Mariia Panasiuk (F)	Ukraine / Ukraine	Student
	Masha Schneider (F)	Slovakia / -	Researcher
	Valentyna Panasiuk (W)	Poland / Ukraine	Student

The 16 teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved 16 Motivation Letters and 16 signed FSTP Declarations) in the 6th round (cut-off date 30.01.2025) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Developing a Smart Color Identification Online/Mobile App

4610193	Ibrahim Shaglil (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Md Fahim Harun (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Valentina Temnik (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Development and Execution of a Social Media Strategy for Tower Spa

8570291	Ana Arsovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sanket Singh (M)	Hungary / Slovenia	Student
	Stefan Stojanovski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant

9550293	Margareth CP Pariguana (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Meta Švagelj (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Ujmir Uka (M)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student

Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

12600304	Md Amine El Bourari (M)	Lithuania / Spain	Student
	Luka Polanič (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Vanessa Efremova (F)	UK / UK	Student

New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare

11300202	Adrijana Minić (F)	Slovenia / Montenegro	Student
	Gašper Korošec (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marija Koleva (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Minela Kaltak (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Protective working equipment

4160181	Mayssae Choukri (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	Makhosi Khuzwayo (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Sahar Hattab (W)	Tunisia / Hungary	Student

Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation

2230311	Karla Marinović (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Marko Jovanović (M)	Serbia / -	Researcher
	Sandra Mikić (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Olivera Delic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Tamara Attard (F)	Malta / -	Researcher

Implementation of AI systems in the metal processing industry (small and medium sized production)

4610203	Ibrahim Shaglil (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Kawtar Dhaidah (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	Moenes Benaissa (M)	Tunisia / Hungary	Student
	Noureddine Hfaiedh	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Wafae El Majdoub	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation

10550311	Damjan Georgievski (M)	Belgium / Belgium	Student
	Iva Edrovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Kostadin Mitkov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

11450300	Dragan Jovanovski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sabrina Jurkošek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Maša Čorović (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Recycling 3D printing waste

11430230	Faustin Habimana (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Huzaifa Tahir (M)	Finland / Finland	Student
	Budagodage LN Nadeeshani (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Nima E Gorji (M)	Ireland / -	Researcher

Marketing And Selling Campaigns Based On Market Research

8730145	Shreyash Singh (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Yeliena Bemeshchuk (F)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Sviatoslav Novosad (M)	Ukraine / Hungary	Student
	Dorina Péntek (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia

9650247	Dino Andreevski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Jana Jovanoska (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Jovana Asterija Nakova (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Virtual Bar Caffee: Functional Development, Optimiiization and SEO Strategy

11830289	Hoimonti Choudhury (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Ritoprovo Roy (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Lali Kurdadze (F)	Georgia / Georgia	Student
	Pradyumna Kapure (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Md Farid (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies

12300190	Tea Papec (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Una Sekulović (F)	Montenegro / Slovenia	Student
	Zdravko Brdarovski (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing

11450150	Ivana Kisin (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Maša Ćorović (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Vasil Stojanov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

The 25 teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved 25 Motivation Letters and 25 signed FSTP Declarations) in the 7th round (cut-off date 28.02.2025) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

WATER AND ENERGY SAVING IN AQUATICS CENTRES FACILITIES

12120165	Ajhan Skenderoski (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Daniel Pereira (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student
	Slavica Dimkoska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Airbridge Go To Market

11520296	Ajhan Skenderoski (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Filip Bojinović (M)	Serbia / Slovenia	Student
	Slavica Dimkoska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably

11820179	Ariana Sadiku (F)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student
	Ana Dragić (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Md Fahim Harun (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student

Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation

10420311	Lučka Kaligarič (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Martina Mileva (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marija Ristovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Vanja Angjelovikj (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marko Arsov (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student

AI Avatar Interactive Learning System for Cutting-Edge EdTech Platform

12310123	Nik Kos (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Olha Sanko (F)	Ukraine / -	Researcher
	Viktor Tikhonov (M)	Ukraine / -	Researcher
	Vicktoriya Tonoyan (F)	Ukraine / Ukraine	Student
	Viktor Bortsevich (M)	Ukraine / Ukraine	Student
	Yuehan John (W)	Finland / Finland	Student

Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

4410300	Ahlam Boubekri (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	Ahmad Asaad (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Parnian Kashani (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

11650300	Ivana Kisin (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Md Fahim Harun (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Tanja Gošnjak (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers

4410255	Ahlam Boubekri (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	Dániel Simon Berkesi (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Parnian Kashani (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

13590304	Blerina Hasani (F)	Kosovo / Kosovo	Student
	Eva Simonič (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Gjorgi Andonovski (M)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student

BossFacade-EcoFacade

13680258	Alaa Abbadi (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Iva Dimitrievska (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Nikolina Landeka (F)	Bosnia / Bosnia	Student

Crack the code: Help us connect with the next gen of learners online

9510233	Mohamad Ali Hijazi (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Pavel Aftimiciuc (M)	Moldova / Hungary	Student
	Nasibakhon Rasulova (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Zahraa Hijazi (F)	France / France	Student

Bioprinting - future technology for tissues and drugs

13380231	Evgenija Kolovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Juš Smole (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Tjaša Šentjurc (F)	UK / UK	Student

Educational Center at Greenagro

12670227	Diana Vicente (F)	Portugal / Portugal	Student
	Filipe Santos (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student
	Muhammad Ahsan Yaseen (M)	Italy / Italy	Student

Illuminating the Invisible: UV-visible Marking on Recycled Paper

10030313	Martina Mileva (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marija Ristovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Vanja Angjelovikj (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Marko Arsov (M)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student

Forecasting and predicting customer's behaviour and their ability for repaying their obligations

9200237	Ivana Kisin (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Mustafa Bekmezci (M)	Turkey / -	Researcher
	Stefanos Heikki Panagiotou (M)	Greece / Greece	Student
	Yasin Sahin (M)	Turkey / Turkey	Student

Internationalisation of Greenagro products and services

12980226	Lucija Kostanić (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Maksim Dovečar (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Muhammad Ahsan Yaseen (M)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Mirjana Nedelkovska (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student

Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications

13390235	Aleksandra Vrkačević (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Gjorgi Andonovski (M)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Marko Gorenak (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Leja Rebolj (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Innovative B2B Solutions Through Cross-Industry Collaboration Challenge

12640301	Ahmad Asaad (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Najwa El majdoub (F)	Morocco / Morocco	Student
	Kawtar Dhaidah (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Noureddine Hfaiedh (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications

12450235	Adam Grzywaczyk (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Branislav Trudic (M)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Emma Olmi (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Natalia Burlaga (F)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Zuzanna Styrna (F)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Wojciech Smutek (M)	Poland / -	Researcher

Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

7580304	Gabriela Suša (W)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Jelena Grujicic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Sara Epet (W)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Tal Ben Shalom (M)	Israel / Israel	Student

MCO Marketing Campaign (Marketing Campaign)

7430170	Blerina Hasani (F)	Kosovo / Kosovo	Student
	Gašper Gortnar (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Andreja Šormaz (F)	Bosnia / Bosnia	Student

Educational LinkedIn Campaign: Recycling Facts, Myths, and Proper Waste Sorting Practices

13620214	Gustavo Raiser Micheli (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Jiara Laine Montaño (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Kornkanok Keardsap (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Pedr Monteiro (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student

Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging

12670240	Ana Dragić (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Ariana Sadiku (F)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student
	Filipe Santos (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student

Project 1: Product Utilizing Post-Production Re grind

4470239	Edita Dvořáková (F)	Czechia / Czechia	Student
	Najwa El majdoub (F)	Morocco / Morocco	Student
	Muhammad Hamza Daud (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging

12540240	Edita Dvořáková (F)	Czechia / Czechia	Student
	Georgios Koutsikas (M)	Greece / Greece	Student
	Shubhanshu Singh (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

The twelve teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved twelve Motivation Letters and twelve signed FSTP Declarations) in the 8th round (cut-off date 31.03.2025) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Innovative Marketing and Sales Campaigns of the Future for HORPOL

12140317	Ivana Koleva (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Anđela Mrđa (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Vasil Stojanov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

14410300	Md Hanbal Abdullatheef (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Nadja Klimenta (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Urša Švigelj (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Crack the code: Help us connect with the next gen of learners online

13930233	Ana Taseva (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Eva Toplišek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Isidora Marković (W)	Serbia / Slovenia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably Malsch TechnoValuation

12540179	Edita Dvořáková (F)	Czechia / Czechia	Student
	Georgios Koutsikas (M)	Greece / Greece	Student
	Shubhanshu Singh (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

14640292	Amadea Iva Delopst (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Gabriele Grilli (M)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Kosta Jovanovic (M)	Bosnia / Bosnia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably

12670179	Filipe Santos (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student
	Maksim Dovečar (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Muhammad Ahsan Yaseen (M)	Italy / Italy	Student

Post-production process automation: Designing a system for the automatic removal of supports and surface smoothing of 3D prints.

11430232	Farbod Rokni (M)	Austria / Austria	Student
	Gülcan Bal (F)	Turkey / Turkey	Student
	Huzaifa Tahir (M)	Finland / Finland	Student

AEPAP: From Advanced Engineering Prototypes To Actual Production

11430180	Fenteng Eric Agyei Owusu (M)	France / France	Student
	Huzaifa Tahir (M)	Finland / Finland	Student
	Budagodage L.N Nadeeshani (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Business plan for a digital tool on healthy urban planning

13980169	Md Hanbal Abdullatheef (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Nikolina Topić (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Sara Slamnik (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Innovation Ecosystem Matchmaking Platform: Expert-Innovator Connection Hub for Technology Commercialization

15090308	Idrissa Maiga (W)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Luka Taslak (M)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Norina Vigh (F)	Netherlands / Netherlands	Student

ReSoil® Website Digital Optimization, SEO Strategy, and User Engagement

7500310	Angelina Apostoloska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Borko Petrevski (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Stefana Spirkoska (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student

Elevating Tower Spa's Brand Through Engaging Digital Content

8570350	Ana Arsovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sanket Singh (M)	Hungary / Slovenia	Student
	Stefan Stojanovski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

The 58 teams selected by companies (corresponding to approved 58 Motivation Letters and 58 signed FSTP Declarations) in the 9th round (cut-off date 15.04.2025) of the Call for Students and Researchers:

Young People Live Sustainably

13640179	Gustavo Raiser Micheli (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Jiara Laine Montaño (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Kornkanok Keardsap (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Pedro Monteiro (M)	Portugal / Portugal	Student

Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia

14010247	Ivan Andonovski (M)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Eva Toplišek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Nikolina Topić (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Hoply: Safe, and affordable rides for kids, simplifying after-school transportation for families

15290335	Igor Arsov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Gordana Petkovska (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Mia Jakimovska (F)	Spain / Spain	Student

Office of the future: tech to wellbeing

15230164	Enrico Rigamonti (M)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Godfried Adaba (M)	UK / -	Researcher
	George-Marian Tudose (M)	Romania / Romania	Student
	Karina Trelles (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Nathaniel Amoah (M)	UK / -	Researcher

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

15380292	Farhan Ali (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Sana Ullah (M)	Spain / Lithuania	Student
	Jelena Pecelj (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers

15150255	Vladimir Georgievski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Emili Koshulcheva (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sara Mitkovska (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Sofija Stojanova (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Toshe Dimov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Personalized Innovation Funding Alert System: Intelligent Newsletter Platform for Research Competitions

15090307	Idrissa Maiga (W)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Luka Taslak (M)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Norina Vigh (F)	Netherlands / Netherlands	Student

Energy-related regulation scenarios in Europe in 2030

14540288	Alina Maria Vaduva (F)	UK / -	Researcher
	Daniel Balsalobre Lorente (M)	Spain / -	Researcher
	Muhammet Demirbilek (M)	Turkey / -	Researcher
	Mirela Panait (F)	Romania / -	Researcher
	Samantha Reid (F)	UK / UK	Student
	Riccardo Bigi (M)	Italy / UK	Student

AI-Powered EU Grant Advisory Platform Development for Scientific Innovations

15090306	Idrissa Maiga (W)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Sonay Karaaslan (F)	Turkey / Turkey	Student
	Norina Vigh (F)	Netherlands / Netherlands	Student

Development Of A Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System

13560109	Egzona Osmani (F)	Kosovo / N. Macedonia	Student
	Kassie Tesfaye Mengie (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Zahraa Hijazi (F)	France / France	Student

New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant

14410293	Md Hanbal Abdullatheef (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Nadja Klimenta (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Urša Švagelj (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Office of the future: tech to wellbeing

15290164	Igor Arsov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Gordana Petkovska (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student
	Mia Jakimovska (F)	Spain / Spain	Student
	Jana Belichevska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Development Of A Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System

2710109	Izabel Peternel (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Nelby Brañez Ramos (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Md Mehedi Hasan (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student

Bioprinting - future technology for tissues and drugs

6490231	Alexandru G-Grigorescu (M)	Romania / Romania	Student
	Alexia Ecaterina Cârstea (F)	Romania / Romania	Student
	João Malta Barbosa (M)	Portugal / -	Researcher
	Lucian Toma Ciocan (M)	Romania / -	Researcher
	Marco Truccato (M)	Italy / -	Researcher
	Robert Ancuceanu (M)	Romania / -	Researcher

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

15590292	Andrej Kasura (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Benzaid Salma (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	Fatima-ezzahra Mabchour (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"

13830347	Berat Sinani (M)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student
	Jovana Ivanovic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Matej Međugorac (M)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services

13830329	Ivan Andonovski (M)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Jovana Ivanovic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Matej Međugorac (M)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

16170292	Lindrit Krasniqi (M)	Kosovo / Slovenia	Student
	Lucijana Kraljevic (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Julija Miladinovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Cellulose Reinvented

15810346	Andrzej Baziak (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Anja Dujković (F)	Bosnia / Bosnia	Student
	Dragana Stevic (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Developing & Testing a Low-Cost Sustainable Insulation or Monitoring Solution for Temperature-Sensitive Logistics

15760354	Md Mazedur Rahman (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Pritam Chowdhury (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Swastika Roy (F)	Spain / -	Researcher

Innovative Skincare Formulation: Advanced Research and Optimization

10360348	Karla Marinović (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Olivera Delić (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Sandra Mikić (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Tamara Attard (F)	Malta / -	Researcher

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

15220292	Maciej Zagórski (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Nika Horvat (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Patricia Pavleković (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

The Global Perfusion Gaming Tournament

1522094	Maciej Zagórski (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Nika Horvat (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Patricia Pavleković (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"

12190347	Kristijan Stefanoski (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Tea Papec (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Una Sekulović (F)	Montenegro / Slovenia	Student

New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant

14880293	Ivan Križič (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Lindrit Krasniqi (M)	Kosovo / Slovenia	Student
	Pia Popovič (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably

14530179	Annalisa Musto (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Claudio Pontillo (M)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Filomena Izzo (F)	Italy / -	Researcher
	Ozlem Ozdemir (F)	UK / -	Researcher
	Mubabela Ndaye (M)	UK / UK	Student

Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors

14880103	Ivan Križič (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Pia Popovič (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Raheleh Soltanibahreman (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors

15790103	Md Mazedur Rahman (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Pritam Chowdhury (M)	Germany / Germany	Student
	Swastika Roy (F)	Spain / -	Researcher

Young People Live Sustainably

15800179	Anja Kumer Lapornik (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Mohammed Aslam (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Mohammed A.B. Abdulla (M)	UK / UK	Student

Digital Music Education Innovation

15220213	Maciej Zagórski (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Nika Horvat (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Patricia Pavleković (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare

11300300	Adrijana Minić (F)	Montenegro / Montenegro	Student
	Marija Koleva (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Minela Kaltak (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Creating a B2B Marketing Campaign for High-Quality decoration cosmetic packaging and plastic components various industries

14700364	Ivana Koleva (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Anđela Mrđa (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Nikolche Gjorgjievski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Developing Sustainable Event Services and Methodology for Restaurants

12980294	Erik Curk (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Lucija Kostanić (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Mirjana Nedelkowska (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student

Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

15620304	Anabela Jelača (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Ivan Atanasov (M)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Nikolche Gjorgjievski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

8700304	Dragan Jovanovski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Sabrina Jurkošek (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Mirjana Nedelkowska (F)	North Macedonia / Slovenia	Student

Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z"

3990347	Mohamed Amine El Bourari (M)	Spain / Spain	Student
	Hanif Ahmad (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Vanesa Efremova (F)	UK / UK	Student

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

8730292	Dorina Péntek (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Sani Ahmed (M)	Czech Republic / -	Researcher
	Shreyash Singh (M)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Theodore Newman (M)	Germany / -	Researcher

Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion

15520304	Eszter Borsodi (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student
	Daniel Gojković (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Nadja Klimenta (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector

15630292	Anabela Jelača (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Ivan Atanasov (M)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Nikolche Gjorgjievski (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Young People Live Sustainably

14030179	Boban Nikolov (M)	North Macedonia / Spain	Student
	Guillermo McC. Valderrama (M)	Spain / UK	Student
	Pilar García García (F)	Spain / Spain	Student

Airbridge Go To Market

15380296	Farhan Ali (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Sana Ullah (M)	Spain / Lithuania	Student
	Jelena Pecelj (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Microelectronic Industry PCB boards recycling (PCB-REC)

13680345	Andrzej Baziak (M)	Poland / Poland	Student
	Nikolina Landeka (F)	Bosnia / Bosnia	Student
	Tijana Kremenović (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student

Eco-Friendly Solvents for Cosmetics: Harnessing the Power of DES

10550349	Damjan Georgievski (M)	Belgium / Belgium	Student
	Iva Edrovska (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Kostadin Mitkov (M)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies

16120190	Ana Barišić (F)	Croatia / Croatia	Student
	Kristijan Stefanoski (W)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Natália Natália Konkolyová (F)	Slovakia / Hungary	Student

Review of New Restrictions on Product Packaging and Labeling and Analysis of Impact on the Market

14350355	Berat Sinani (M)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student
	Jelena Pecelj (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Sara Slamnik (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student

Croatian market research regarding the sale of concrete products

13830312	Berat Sinani (M)	Kosovo / North Macedonia	Student
	Jovana Ivanović (F)	Serbia / Serbia	Student
	Matej Međugorac (M)	Croatia / Croatia	Student

Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ"

16190173	Dounia Aamoum (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Antonija Andonovski (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Andrey Hilyadnikov (M)	Bulgaria / North Macedonia	Student

Shaping the Future of Machine Efficiency: Understanding Customer Needs for OEE Optimization

14130199	Angela Andonovski (F)	North Macedonia / Spain	Student
	Federico Centofanti (M)	Italy / Spain	Student
	Pepa Guerrero Mayo (F)	Spain / Spain	Student

Airbridge Go To Market

14640296	Amadea Iva Delopst (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Mohammed Aslam (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Mohammed A. B. Abdulla (M)	UK / UK	Student

Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation

15230341	Alina Maria Vaduva (F)	UK / -	Researcher
	Enrico Rigamonti (M)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Godfried Adaba (M)	UK / -	Researcher
	George-Marian Tudose (M)	Romania / Romania	Student
	Karina Trelles (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Nathaniel Amoah (M)	UK / -	Researcher

Market analysis and trendspotting of automotive lighting products with focus on end customer

16190161	Dounia Aamoum (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Antonija Andonovski (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Andrey Hilyadnikov (M)	Bulgaria / North Macedonia	Student

Marketing campaign for metal-forming defects sensors

16190261	Dounia Aamoum (F)	Italy / Italy	Student
	Antonija Andonovski (F)	N. Macedonia / N. Macedonia	Student
	Andrey Hilyadnikov (M)	Bulgaria / North Macedonia	Student

Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation

14030341	Boban Nikolov (M)	North Macedonia / Spain	Student
	Guillermo McC. Valderrama (M)	Spain / UK	Student
	Pilar García García (F)	Spain / Spain	Student

Enhancing digital marketing of a small International Fiscal & Law Firm

14030208	Boban Nikolov (M)	North Macedonia / Spain	Student
	Guillermo McC. Valderrama (M)	Spain / UK	Student
	Pilar García García (F)	Spain / Spain	Student

Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services

(previously: Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z")

15590347	Andrej Kasura (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
	Salma Benzaid (F)	Morocco / Hungary	Student
	Fatima-ezzahra Mabchour (F)	Hungary / Hungary	Student

MARKETING CAMPAIGN OF THE FUTURE

15830205	Ilyas El (M)	Germany / Lithuania	Student
	Izabel Peternel (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Uzair Qazi (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student

MARKETING CAMPAIGN OF THE FUTURE

15850205	Anja Kumer Lapornik (F)	Slovenia / Slovenia	Student
	Mohammed Aslam (M)	Lithuania / Lithuania	Student
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15320176	Roshid Md Abdul (M)	Hungary / -	Researcher
	Avrupa Birliđi (M)	Turkey / Turkey	Student
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	Tamás Németh (M)	Hungary / -	Researcher

IV. FINAL REMARKS AND CONCLUSIONS

The deliverable lists selected co-creation teams during the nine rounds of the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers, and published company Challenges during the entire project. 145 companies have published a total of 251 Challenges. The successfully initiated co-creation projects and the variety in team assembly (including gender diversity and residency) demonstrated the potential of the INDUSAC project for establishing industry-academia collaborations.

V. LIST OF REFERENCES

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VI. TABLE OF CHANGES TO THE PREVIOUS VERSION

page 2	updated History of Changes
page 3	summary of the project modified to express actions taken instead of planned
page 4	Abstract updated to include results obtained during the entire project
page 7	Introduction updated to include results from the entire project; definition of 'approved' and 'selected' is added
pages 8-18	list of Challenges rewritten in a condensed format;
pages 13-18	added list of 122 Challenges published from September 2024 through March 2025
pages 21, 23	updated numbers of teams following a revision (one team was removed because they hadn't proceeded with the co-creation project, another was moved from the 2 nd to 1 st round of projects, and a third team was removed because it had been duplicated by accident
pages 25-41	added list of 124 teams approved by companies in subsequent rounds of the Call for Students and Researchers
page 42	Final Remarks and Conclusions updated to include results from the entire project

